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USING EDUCATIONAL VIDEO GAMES TO ENHANCE ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN MATHEMATICS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the effects of educational video games on students' academic achievement in mathematics. The study was carried out on 62 students in class 9th at Alagappa Model Higher Secondary School, Karaikudi, Sivagangai, Tamil Nadu. The purposive sampling technique was used to select the samples. The Achievement Test on Mathematics (ATM) was used to collect relevant data. The intervention programme for five weeks was given to the experimental group students. The analysis was done after the intervention programme and found that the experimental group achieved more academically than the control group

Keywords: Educational video games, academic achievement, mathematics, secondary school students.

Introduction

An Educational Video Game (EVG) is a video game that provides learning or training value to the player. Video games have the potential to contribute to all three major fields of psychology: affective (awakening feelings), cognate (aggressive or impulsive behavior), and cognitive (learning-related skills) (Miguel de Aguilera, 2003). Video games have been demonstrated to improve working memory, mental rotation skills, and geometry performance (Elena Novak, 2015). Some valuable features of educational video games include a clear goal, an adequate difficulty level, quick-moving stimuli, and integrated instructions (Robillard M, 2014).

The rapid penetration of increasingly sophisticated technologies into every facet of society is causing significant shifts in how, when, and where we work, how individuals, companies, and even nations understand and organize themselves, and how educational systems should be structured to prepare students effectively for life in the 21st century. School-aged children worldwide are growing up immersed in a media-rich, ubiquitous, "always connected" world. Concerns over the need to reform the educational system to effectively prepare students for a much more technology-driven, interconnected and competitive "flat world" are being voiced by politicians, educators, parents, and others across the globe (Reimers, 2008; Burke, 2010). Continuing to provide the same types of

education to students as the world continues to change will not serve them well.

Present-day men have attained the status of e-civilization, which may have a significant impact on society in general and students in particular. Instructors, parents, and public authorities are astonished by how dropout rates have grown in education at all levels for years. This alarming trend suggests a drastic decrease in the motivation of students towards learning. Several hypotheses have been formulated to explain this controversial issue. In this line, several authors like Prensky (Prensky, 2001) argue there is a clear disconnection between students' expectations and what they receive in the classroom. According to Prensky, current students are digital natives—people used to interacting with rich interactive digital media such as computers, mobile devices, or video game consoles; this differs from the typical pedagogical strategies in terms of content and interaction. (Prensky, 2001; Aldrich, 2005).

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To tackle this issue, a deep reform should come to the educational system, updating the content and interactivity used to support learning. One of the proposals is the use of video games and other kinds of interactive technological content. The application of games in education is a trend on the rise. There is a belief that video games have the potential to enhance the learning process in multiple ways. One of the most frequently discussed is the ability of games to increase students' motivation towards learning as they can capture their attention and keep them engaged and immersed (Gee, 2003; Malone, 1981). Other interesting traits of educational video games are that they provide immersive in-game worlds that can be explored freely by the students, promoting self-directed learning (Squire, 2003), their short feedback cycles with a perception of progress (Freitas and Oliver, 2006), or their relation to constructivist theories and support of scaffolded learning (Prensky, 2001).

Since educational video games made their "breakthrough" towards the attention of teachers and scientists alike, many researchers have tried to evaluate the usefulness of specific game play characteristics for educational purposes (Dickey, 2005). So the investigator decided to conduct a study on the effect of educational video games on enhancing academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students.

Objective

To study the effectiveness of using educational video games on academic achievement in mathematics among secondary school students.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There is no significant difference between control and experimental group students in their pre test scores on achievement in mathematics.
2. There is no significant difference between control and experimental group students in their post test scores on achievement in mathematics.

Method

Design of the study

This research was conducted with 62 secondary school students in class 9th who were being educated in

the 2019-2020 academic session. In the mathematics subject, an intervention programme based on educational video game learning is used. There are two groups: experimental groups comprised of 31 secondary school students and control groups of 31 students. The lessons were carried out in the experimental group by using educational video games and traditional methods in the control group. The achievement test in mathematics is applied before and after the intervention programme to both groups.

Tools used

In this study, an Achievement Test in Mathematics (ATM) constructed and validated by the investigator was used. It consists of 40 questions. The respondents were awarded 1 point for each correct answer and 0 for the wrong answer. The pilot study was done on 50 students, and the Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was calculated. The reliability was found to be 0.65.

Analysis and interpretation

Hypothesis 1: There is no significance difference between control and experimental group students in their pre test scores on achievement in mathematics.

Table 1
Difference between control group and experimental group students in their pre test scores on achievement in mathematics

Groups	N	Mean	SD	calculated value of 't'	Remark at 5% level
Control	31	44.65	5.65	0.36	NS
Experimental	31	44.62	6.28		

Table 1 reveals that the mean scores of control and experimental group students in the pre-test on achievement in mathematics are 44.65 and 44.62, respectively, with SDs of 5.652 and 6.28. The calculated 't' value is 0.36, which is not significant both at the 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. That means there is no significant difference between the scores gained by

control and experimental group students on achievement in mathematics before the intervention programme.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significance difference between control and experimental group students in their post test scores on achievement in mathematics.

Table 2

Difference between control group and experimental groups students in their post test scores on achievement in mathematics

Groups	N	Mean	SD	Calculated value of 't'	Remark at 5% level
Control	31	43.98	5.92	2.14	S
Experimental	31	45.43	5.831		

It is revealed from table 2 that the mean scores of the control and experimental groups are found to be 43.98 and 45.43, respectively, with a standard deviation of 5.92 and 5.831. The calculated 't' value is found to be 2.14 which is significant at the 0.01 level of significance. That means educational video games have a significant effect on the achievement in mathematics of secondary school students. Hence, the hypothesis that there is no significant difference between control and experimental group students in their scores on the achievement in mathematics test in the post-test is retained.

Discussion and conclusion

Educational video games are considered interactive, user-oriented, and motivating learning instruments, allowing the delivery of tailored learning experiences. Designing and implementing adaptive and personalised educational video games can become a suitable tool for teachers in the student-centric teaching and learning process. Even though video games are rarely considered by teachers and educators, some of them could be stimulating texts in promoting gender equality. One of the most influential and recent media to promote gender standards to children, young adults, and adults is video games. Despite this, research on the portrayal of gender identity in video games, and their influence on gender education is still in its early stages. For this reason, some of the pedagogical potentials of

video games have been explored in this contribution, focusing mainly on gender socialization.

The implementation of educational video games in education has been a priority trend in educational reform today. As a result, schools and government institutions should engage in active participation, initiatives, and goodwill in order to implement and improve learning through educational video games. The findings of this study revealed a positive effect of using educational video games on student achievement in mathematics among secondary school students. Students who were taught through educational video games were better than students taught through the traditional method of teaching.

This educational video game learning method allows students to make connections between everyday events and various mathematical concepts. This type of study should also be conducted on other subjects and presented to teachers for their use. Prior knowledge of the teachers' about the students is essential for effective teaching. Teachers may be trained to develop educational video games for teaching and learning. Since this teaching through educational video games is efficient, it can be more emphasised in the curriculum..

References

1. M. Prensky, "Digital natives, digital immigrants." *On the Horizon*. NCB University Press.vol.9,2001.
2. C. Aldrich, *Learning by Doing: A Comprehensive Guide to Simulations, Computer Games, and Pedagogy in e-Learning and Other Educational Experiences*. San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer; 2005.
3. J. P. Gee, *What video games have to teach us about learning and literacy?* New York; Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003.
4. T. Malone, "Toward a Theory of Intrinsically Motivating Instruction," *Cognitive Science*, vol. 5, pp. 333-369, 1981.
5. K. Squire, "Video games in education," *International Journal of Intelligent Simulations and Gaming*, vol. 2, pp. 49-62, 2003.

6. S. de Freitas and M. Oliver, "How can exploratory learning with games and simulations within the curriculum be most effectively evaluated?," *Computers & Education*, vol. 46, pp. 249-264, 2006.

7. M. Prensky, *Digital Game Based Learning*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 2001.

8. Dickey, M. D. (2005). *Engaging by design: How engagement strategies in popular computer and video games can inform instructional design*. *Educational Technology Research & Development*, 53(2), 67-83. DOI:10.1007/BF02504866

9. Reimers, F. M. (2008). *Preparing students for the flat world*. *Education Week*. <http://www.edweek.org/ew/articles/2008/10/08/07reimers.h28.html>

10. Burke, A. (2010). *Teacher as leader in a "flat world": Preparing students in a global community*, *Language Arts Journal of Michigan*, 25(2), 4. <http://scholarworks.gvsu.edu/lajm/vol25/iss2/4>

11. De Aguilera M, Mendiz A. (2003) *Video games and education: (Education in the Face of a "Parallel School")*. *Computers in Entertainment*, 1(1):1-10.

12. Novak E, Tassell J. (2015) *Using video game play to improve education-majors' mathematical performance: An experimental study*. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 53:124-130.

13. Robillard M, Mayer-Crittenden C. (2014) *Use of Technology as an Innovative Approach to Non-Linguistic Cognitive Therapy*. *International Journal of Technologies in Learning*, 20:267-278.

9. Wang, Haertel, and Walberg (1994). *Classroom Presentation*. <https://www.scribd.com/doc/47092297/Classroom-Ecology-Presentation>.

10. Sussman, K., (2012). *Classroom Ecology*. https://hswww.s3.amazonaws.com/11-14-2012/ecology_classroom-11-14-2012/

11. Tanenbaum (2018). *Seven Principles for Inclusive Education*. <https://studentsatthecenterhub.org/resource/the-seven-principles-for-inclusive-education/>

12. Väyrynen, S., (2016). *Principles of Inclusive Education*. <https://www.ulapland.fi/loader.aspx?id=99912612-5d3a-4f3e-80d4-00be61283067>.

13. European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education (2012). *Profile of Inclusive Teachers*. Odense, Denmark: European Agency for Development in Special Needs Education.

14. Wickham, S.,(2012). *The Inclusive and Exclusive Personality Traits*. <http://inspiringbetterlife.blogspot.com/2012/10/the-inclusive-and-exclusive-personality.html>.

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5. NEP 2020: *A comparison with the 1986 education policy* (educationtimes.com)

6. <https://www.economicdiscussion.net/articles/development-of-education-in-india-after-independence/2293#:~:text=Primary%20education%20%20E2%80%93%20been%20free%20and,to%20254%20in%202000%20D01/>

7. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_education_in_the_Indian_subcontinent/

8. <https://thinkstrategicforschools.com/education-21st-century/#:~:text=A%2021st%20century%20education%20is,using%20it%20in%20smart%20ways/>

9. <https://historyplex.com/understanding-cultural-transmission-with-examples/>

10. <https://educationposter.blogspot.com/2016/06/dr-radhakrishnan-education-commission.html>

11. <https://www.tetsuccesskey.com/2017/01/national-policy-of-education-POA-1992.html>

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6. Bupinder Singh, (2015). *Modern Education System: The Pro's And Con's*. <https://bupinder21.wordpress.com/author/bupinder21/>

7. Coleridge (1827). *The Notebooks of Samuel Taylor Coleridge: 1827-1834*, <https://books.google.co.in/books?isbn=0691099073>.

8. Goel. A. and Goel. S.L., (2010). *Quality and Excellence, Encyclopaedia of Higher Education in the 21st Century, Volume 2*, New Delhi: Deep & Deep Publications.